

FEATURES OF TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810969>

Abstract. *this article discusses the linguistic features of phraseological units, their classification, difficulties arising during translation- phraseological units, methods of their translation from English into Uzbek, and also analyzes the application of certain techniques in practice using examples from W. Maugham’s novels “Theater”, “The Moon and the Penny”.*

Keywords: *phraseological unit; phraseology; classification of phraseological units; translation difficulties; translation techniques.*

A phraseological unit is a lexically indivisible unit of language, a stable semantically related combination of words, integral in its meaning, distinguished by imagery, expressiveness, stylistic and emotional coloring, completely or partially rethought. Phraseological units have an evaluative function, that is, they express the speaker’s attitude towards a particular object or phenomenon, give liveliness and expressiveness to speech and are a powerful tool for influencing the audience. There are a large number of classifications of phraseological units, which are based on various criteria. The most famous of them belongs to V.V. Vinogradov. It focuses on the structure of phraseological units and illustrates the varying degrees of dependence of elements and semantic cohesion. According to this classification, phraseological units are divided into phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological combinations. [4, p. 206]

Phraseological fusions are stylistically and emotionally colored, often nationally specific, and also indivisible and have the greatest cohesion of parts. The words that make up them have lost their semantics, so the meanings of phraseological units cannot be derived from the meanings of their constituent elements; their meanings are not motivated. Because of this, it is sometimes difficult to guess the meaning of unfamiliar phraseological fusion. If the translator fails to find an equivalent or analogue of a phraseological unit in the target language, he can convey its meaning using descriptive translation.

Phraseological unities are characterized by imagery and motivation, they are mobile and allow some variability. They are used figuratively, but from their constituent components the meaning of the entire expression can be inferred. When translating, sometimes it is enough to find a correspondence that, although built on a different image, matches in meaning.

Phraseological combinations are stable combinations of words, the meanings of which are composed of the meanings of their constituent components, but one of the words is always used in a figurative meaning. They do not have national specificity, and thanks to the transparency of their internal form and often lack of imagery, it is not difficult to understand their meaning. Phraseological combinations are often translated into words in their literal meaning with the desired stylistic coloring.

It should be noted that phraseological units are considered the most difficult-to-translate lexical category, which is explained by a number of reasons. Firstly, becoming components of a phraseological unit, words with free meaning lose their semantics and acquire a new, related meaning. For this reason, to translate phraseological units, it is not enough to simply select a dictionary correspondence for each component. Secondly, a translator who is new to the phraseology of the original language may find it difficult to recognize phraseological units in the

translation text, which will lead to a word-by-word or literal translation, and this, in turn, to distortion of meaning and subsequent incorrect perception of information by the target audience. It is worth noting here that a translator who is poorly versed in the phraseology of the target language will also inevitably encounter difficulties. They will be associated with finding the equivalent of the original phraseological unit in the target language or selecting an analogue. Thirdly, sometimes even if there is an equivalent phraseological unit in the target language, the translator needs to look for other ways to convey meaning due to the fact that this phraseological unit does not correspond to the context. It is also worth considering that similar phrases in English and Uzbek languages may have different evaluative connotations.

In addition, when translating a phraseological unit, the translator's task is not only to correctly convey its meaning, but also to reflect the emotionally expressive characteristics, evaluative connotation, and functional and stylistic features. Also, the reason for difficulties when translating a phraseological unit can be a high degree of its national specificity. The translator will adapt it to the culture and language of the target audience. Another difficulty is the external similarity of phraseological units in the source and target languages, which have different semantics, which can lead to false associations and incorrect translation.

Let's consider a number of techniques for translating phraseological units and analyze their use in practice, taking as a basis the works of W. Maugham “The Moon and the Penny” [9], “Theater” [8], and their translation into Uzbek by R.Inogomov [6] respectively.

1. Selection of equivalent

Equivalents are divided into full and partial. Full equivalents coincide in everything with the units of the target language: in semantics, imagery, stylistic coloring, component composition, grammatical structure. Partial ones are characterized by slight differences in terms of expression of phraseological units of identical semantics.

Poor lamb, he must be as poor as a church mouse[9, p. 97].

Kambag'alning yettita qorni bor. 6, p. 101].

According to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov [4, p.206], this phraseological unit is translated, the author used partial equivalent in Uzbek. These two phraseological units have the same semantics, component composition and functional and stylistic features. In our opinion, the translation was done successfully. We can also offer another translation option for this phraseological unit: “penniless.”

2. Selection of an analogue

The number of equivalents in the English and Uzbek languages is small, so you often have to resort to searching for analogues, phraseological units that convey the same meaning, but are based on a different image.

What he said had a hateful truth in it, and another defect of my character is that I enjoy the company of those, however depraved, who can give me a Roland for my Oliver[9, p.130].

U halokatli haqiqatni ifoda etdi. Men odamlarni yaxshi ko'raman, garchi ular yomon bo'lsa ham, lekin u so'z uchun cho'ntak kovlamaydi [6, p. 142].

According to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov [4, p. 206], given phraseological unit belongs to the category of phraseological adjuncts. Due to the lack of an equivalent of this English phraseological unit in the Uzbek language, the translator selected an analogue for it, based on a different image. She was forced to refuse to convey the image of the original phraseology. Its preservation and literal translation would be incomprehensible to the Uzbek reader, since national specifics can be traced here: Roland and Oliver - characters from the French heroic poem "The

Song of Roland" who fought each other, but, since their forces were equal, neither of them won. However, the semantics of the Uzbek phraseological unit in the translation text differs from the semantics of the phraseological unit in the original text.

The expression “lekin u so’z uchun cho’ntak kovlamaydi” usually characterizes a person who can carry on a conversation casually and easily, be witty and quickly find answers. In English phraseology, it is emphasized that a person can parry and fight back. The version proposed by the translator is somewhat inaccurate, but can be considered successful, since it conveys most of the information contained in the original. This phraseological unit can also be translated as “give a worthy answer”, “successfully parry”. In cases where it is not possible to find equivalents or analogues of phraseological units, non-phraseological means are used.

3. Descriptive translation

Descriptive translation represents a special lexical replacement with additions, that is, the meaning of a phraseological unit is conveyed using free phrases using explanations, comparisons, and descriptions. It is resorted to when the target language lacks an equivalent and analogue of the original phraseological unit. Sometimes a translator has to resort to explanations due to differences in cultural and linguistic realities in order to facilitate the perception of the translation text by people of a different culture.

It had been done when he took silk and it represented him in a wig and gown. Even they could not make him imposing... [9, p. 14].

U hozirgina qirol advokati bo'lgan va marosim uchun parik va ko'ylak kiygan holda suratga olingan, ammo bu ham uni ta'sirchan ko'rinishga olib kelmadi [6, p. 16].

According to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov [4, p.206], this phraseological unit belongs to the category of phraseological adjuncts. In this case, the translator used descriptive translation. In the original we see metaphor, but the translator was forced to abandon it during translation. Its preservation and literal translation of the phraseological unit as “dressing in silk” would be incomprehensible to the Uzbek reader, since national specifics are clearly visible here. In Great Britain, ordinary lawyers who appear in court wear a cloth robe, while royal ones wear a silk robe, for this reason their entry into office is called “to take silk.” In our opinion, the translation was done successfully.

4. Lexical translation

Lexical translation or replacement is resorted to when in the source language a concept is designated by a phraseological unit, and in the translating language by a lexeme.

He'd be a bit surly sometimes, but when we hadn't had a bite since morning, and we hadn't even got the price of a lie down at the Chink's, he'd be as lively as a cricket [9, With. 158].

Ba'zan u, albatta, qovog'ini solardi, lekin agar ertalabdan kechgacha og'zimizda bir tomchi shudring suvi solmasakda va xitoyliklarga tunash uchun to'lov qilmasakda, u shunchaki ming'iyida kulib qo'yardi. [6, p. 142].

According to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov [4, p. 206], given phraseological unit belongs to the category of phraseological unities. In this case, we are dealing with lexical translation, since the phraseological unit we are considering is translated into Uzbek by one lexical unit. In addition, there is a rethinking of it by the author. In our opinion, this led to semantic inaccuracy: in the original, according to the author’s idea, this phraseological unit emphasizes that, despite the difficult situation, the hero does not lose heart and remains cheerful, which is not reflected in the translation. We can suggest editing the translation as follows: “Sometimes, of course, he frowned, but even when we didn’t have a drop of poppy dew in our mouths from

morning to evening and had nothing to pay the Chinese for the night, he did not lose heart/remained cheerful.”

5. Contextual translation

Contextual translation is the selection of a contextual correspondence to a phraseological unit that is logically related to it and different from the dictionary one.

It's a smack in the eye of course, it's no good denying that, but the only thing is to grin and bear it [9, p. 138].

Albatta, bahslashishning hojati yo'q, bu g'ururga zarba, lekin men nima qila olaman? Tabassum qiling va tamom va shu tarzda omon qolamiz[6, p. 140].

According to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov [4, p. 206], given phraseological unit belongs to the category of phraseological unities. This phraseological unit is metaphorical, relates to colloquial vocabulary and is often translated into Uzbek as "qattiq umidsizlik", "zarba", "bezovta", "muammo". In this case, the translator resorted to contextual translation and complete replacement of the image. In our opinion, the translation was completed successfully and without any loss of meaning.

6. Antonymous translation

Antonymous translation is the translation of a phraseological unit of the source language into phraseological units with opposite semantics, as well as the transformation of an affirmative construction into a negative one and vice versa.

... and with the possibility that Michael might be killed at any moment - it was true he said he was as safe as a house, he only said that to reassure her, and even generals were killed sometimes - if she was to go on living she must have a child by him [9, p. 59].

... u hech qanday xavf ostida emasliginini tushuntirdi, hatto generallar ham o'ldirilgan - faqat uning bolasi uni hayotda saqlab qolishi mumkin edi.[6, p. . 58].

According to the classification of V.V. Vinogradov [4, p.206], given phraseological unit belongs to the category of phraseological unities, since its components are metaphorical and are used in a figurative meaning. In this case, we see that the translator decided to sacrifice the image, since it would remain incomprehensible to the Uzbek reader, and resort to antonymic translation. We consider this translation option to be successful. If you do not use an antonymic translation, this phraseological unit can be translated as follows: “out of danger”, “in complete safety”. However, taking into account the context, which is important here, we believe that the version proposed by the translator sounds more appropriate. In this passage we are talking about the main character’s husband, who volunteered for the front, and when taking part in hostilities, it is hardly possible to remain “out of danger” or “completely safe.” However, in another context, these options do exist.

So, phraseology is a complex phenomenon that requires special attention from translators, since phraseological units are not simple phrases with free meanings of components and a number of difficulties can be encountered when translating them. Our analysis made it possible to verify that in each specific case the translation strategy varies and a number of factors can influence the translation. These include the peculiarities of the use of a phraseological unit in a particular context, its structure, semantics, emotional and expressive coloring. Depending on the situation and features of a phraseological unit, the translator can find an equivalent, analogue, use descriptive, lexical, contextual, antonymic translation and so on. In order to carry out a high-quality translation, the translator must be well acquainted with the above-mentioned techniques for translating phraseological units.

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